

Original Research

Impacts of Non-Tariff Barriers to International Trade on the Growth of Small Business in Tanzania

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Abstract

International trade is a vital component of the global economy. However, to realise sustainable benefits of international trade, a national's external trade policy must identify the non-tariff barriers (NTB) and tariff barriers that hinder small business from participating in international trade and enhance their growth. Though NTBs are largely believed to restrict trade, there is evidence suggesting that NTBs facilitates trade, and provide small businesses a chance to participate in international trade and grow. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between NTBs and sales growth of small business in Tanzania. This study applied correlational design to analyze quantitative data quantitative collected from managers/owners of small businesses selected using stratified sampling technique. The data was gathered using structured questionnaire from 240 managers/owners of small businesses in Temeke and Ubungu districts of Dar es Salaam City. The quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive and multiple linear regression model to ascertain the relationship between NTBs and sales growth of small business. The findings of this study indicate that, three variables of technical barriers to trade, namely, quality management certification, sanitary and phytosanitary and packaging and labelling have positive and significant association with sales growth of small business, while custom procedures has negative and significant link with sales growth of small business. On the contrary, certificate of origin and product certification were found to have non-significant relationship with sales growth of small business.

Keywords: International trade markets, non-tariff barriers to trade technical barriers to trade.

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Introduction

Globally, international trade has increased among many trading countries largely due to increase in global population and transformation of the world business system (Ortiz-Ospina et al., 2018). Multilateral agreements, trade integrations are among the major transformations adopted in the world business today (Cali et al., 2019) with the aim to increase trade volume among trading partner countries (Ajewole et al., 2022; Durán Lima et al., 2021). International trade enables countries earn foreign exchange and thus be able to improve social-economic infrastructures, increase employment and income of the nation, business and individuals (Kahiya & Kadirov, 2020; Nguto, 2020; Puri & Kumar, 2021). However, for a country to realise sustainable benefits of international trade, a national's external trade policy must identify how small entrepreneurs can be included in the process and address the challenges limiting them to participate in international trade.

Worldwide, small businesses are fundamental to socio-economic growth and development for they constitute a largest part of business enterprises (Tukamuhabwa et al., 2021). Currently, it is estimated more than 99% of all businesses in the global are micro and small enterprises (Curado et al., 2018). Small businesses employ 50-70% of workforce worldwide contributing 40% of Gross Domestic Product of countries, and are source of income of poor people and thus reduces poverty (Algan, 2019). Besides their number and the crucial roles, they play in the country's economy, small businesses are more disadvantaged than medium and large businesses and this affect their ability to grow (Nguto, 2020).

Researches shows that tariff and Non-Tariff Barriers (NTB), lack of information, limited financial capacity and lack of trading networks (Dolabella, 2020; Mbo'o-Tchouawou et al., 2019; Ndumbe, 2013) prevent small business from participating in international trade (Mwaniki, 2011). However, according to Dolabella (2020), the NTBs such as quota, complex trade regulations, and requirements of high standards, embargoes, rules of origin, sanctions and licenses have the largest ramification to the participation of small business in international trade, and hence can greatly affect their growth. Thus, the reduction of NTBs of trade can enable small businesses to access external market and improve their profitability and growth (Abushaikha, 2014; Cali & Montfaucon, 2021).

In Europe, in order to ensure small business participate in the external market, European Union (EU) countries use single currency "EURO" and have ratified a resolution for complete economic and monetary union in all aspects (Cali et al., 2019). As a result, intra-EU free exchange, EU regulation and EU competition policy were created (Mustilli & Pelkmans, 2013). The combination of these anti-protectionism reforms in EU countries yields a market environment that is favourable for small business to participate in international trade (Dolabella, 2020). In Africa the efforts to improve international trade through reduction of NTBs have been through among others increasing effective trade integration and agreements (Leyaro, 2021). Other efforts include simplification of trade regimes through policy and practice by lowering the import and export procedures and easing official trade rules, such as exemption of value added tax to product value not exceeding US\$2,000 (Brenton & Soprano, 2018). Despite success still the challenges of small-scale traders to participate in international trade remains at large in Africa (Masinde, 2015).

The East African Community (EAC) member states in order to increase trade volume decided to ratify common customs union procedures and common market strategies (free movement of goods, labour, services and capital), which saw relaxation of NTBs. The establishment involved EAC rules of origin (EAC, 2011), eliminate delays at the border, roadblocks and ports of Mombasa and Dar es Salaam, harmonisation of axle load specification, elimination of varying procedures for issuance of certification marks, inspection and testing through mutual recognition of quality marks by Partner States and establishment of one stop border point (OSBPs) in order to minimize routine logistic activities and duplications of custom procedures across borders (Ndunda, 2013). According to Swaleh (2020), these reforms have improved the state of business among EAC member states. However, the difficulties to access external market persisted among small businesses (Cheruiyot & Rotich, 2018).

In Tanzania, small business together with medium enterprises constitute about 95% of businesses; contribute 35% of Gross Domestic Product and 40% of employment (Nkwabi, 2019). Due to their importance, it has been recently stressed that, small business deserve significant attention (Nkwabi, 2019) and especially in accessing the external market through international trade (Mpunga, 2016; Sanjo & Ibrahim, 2017). Thus, the government has taken critical decisions to improve small businesses' access to external market through anti NTBs arrangements. The arrangements include EAC customs union and common market protocols (Leyaro, 2021), Southern African Development Cooperation [SADC] (Masinde, 2015), the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) of the United States (Cook & Jones, 2021; Simon et al., 2022), and the Everything but Arms (EBA) program of the European Union (Cook & Jones, 2021).

Moreover, as an EAC member state, Tanzania benefits from the establishment of OSBPs with neighbouring states of EAC, and also from Trade and Investment Framework Agreement (TIFA) with the U.S (Zgovu, 2021). Leyaro (2021) revealed that reduction in NTBs due to ratification of AGOA, EBA, TIFA and establishment of OSBPs among EAC member states has boosted trade between Tanzania and rest of the world and the participation of small businesses. This is supported by Gabagambi (2013), Chebon (2019) and Maziku (2019). Principally, the abolishment or reduction in NTBs enables improvement in international trade among the trading partners. Accordingly, Simon et al. (2022), Pichon (2022) and Zgovu (2021) reported that small businesses of Tanzania have benefited with the AGOA, EBA and TIFA. These arrangements allow small businesses to access the U.S., EU, SADC and EAC markets. Researchers acknowledge that these efforts have increased access of small businesses in international trade (Leyaro, 2021; Masinde, 2015; Simon et al., 2022).

Despite the noted efforts and benefits realised, challenges of small businesses to access external market still exist in Tanzania (Masinde, 2015), and still the growth of small businesses is not impressive and rate of failures of new small businesses is very high (Isaya, n.d.; Kazimoto, 2014) while few which survive are struggling financially (Umar et al., 2020). The Economic and Social Research Foundation [ESRF] report of 2015 show that only 36.90% of the small businesses graduate to the higher level in Tanzania. Regardless of the importance of NTBs on the growth of small businesses, the link between NTBs and growth of small businesses has not clearly been established empirically. Most reviewed studies regarding NTBs and small business in Tanzanian context have focused

on the impact of NTBs on access or participation in international trade (Chebon, 2019). Given the importance of small businesses and international trade and to the economy of Tanzania, it is therefore imperative to understand how NTBs affects the growth of small businesses in Tanzania. Therefore, this study intended to examine the influence of NTBs namely technical barrier to trade and specific limitations on trade; on growth of small businesses in Tanzania.

Literature Review

The theoretical foundation of the study

Competitive advantage theory and New Trade theory are used to guide the study to explain the relationship between NTBs and growth of small businesses.

Competitive Advantage Theory

The leading theorist of competitive advantage theory is Michael E. Porter. Competitive advantage theory suggests that everyone is better off if decisions are made based on the competitive advantage at all levels: national, corporate and individuals (Porter, 1998). According to Porter (1985), national prosperity is created, not inherited. Nation prosperity grows with natural endowments in a country, as well as its labour pool, its interest rates, or its value of currency. According to porter (1990), the competitive advantage of nations is the capacity of its industry to innovate and upgrade to form a nation's competitiveness. He believes that success in international trade comes from the four interrelated components, which are factor conditions, demand conditions, related and supporting industries, and firm strategy structure, and rivalry. Porter also concluded that their home environment is the most forward-looking, challenging, and dynamic so that nations succeed in particular industries (Mulugeta Girma Dibiku, 2017).

The theory of competitive advantage is in line with the proposed study because it explains how a country or small business participate and access the foreign market. According to United Nations report (2019), Tanzania small businesses exports onion, maize, oranges, timber wood and other produces to other countries because the country is endowed with huge arable land, supporting cultivation and tree planting, and there is a high demand of that product in external markets. Thus, due to those demand and factor conditions, Tanzanian small businesses have an upper hand when dealing with exportation of agricultural produce to trading partners. On the other hand, Tanzania has been a good importer of industrial products such as electrical equipment, lubricants, vehicle accessories and pharmaceutical products because of the geographical cluster of related industries and innovations. Perceiving new market opportunities can contribute to create a competitive advantage, and thus assist small businesses to access foreign market.

Institutional Theory

Institutional theory was introduced in the late 1970s by John Meyer and Brian Rowan as a way to explore in detail how organizations fit with, are related to, and were shaped by their societal, state, national, and global environments. DiMaggio and Powell (1983) developed further the theory. The theory asserts that the institutional environment can

strongly influence the development of formal structures in an organization. Institutional theory considers the processes by which structures, including schemes; rules, norms, and routines, become established as authoritative guidelines for social behaviour. Adoption and retention of many organizational practices and procedures are often more dependent on social pressures for conformity and legitimacy than on technical pressures for economic performance. Institutional theory is a deeper and more resilient aspect of social structure which consider the processes by which structures includes schemes, rules, norms, and routines, become established an authoritative guideline for social behaviour (E Hassan et al., 2021). The institution theory is just like custom points together with its custom procedures, operational rules and regulations that demand small export traders to comply with in order to access the international market. These include certificate or rules of origin, product certification, quality, safety, packaging and labelling requirements (Brenton & Soprano, 2018; Masinde, 2015).

The Empirical Literature Review

Adarov and Ghodsi (2021) analysed the heterogeneous effects of technical regulations and safety standards embodied in non-tariff measures on foreign direct investment. The authors reveal that Technical Barriers to Trade (TBTs) played a much greater role as trade-inhibiting factor in comparison with import tariffs and sanitary and phytosanitary (SPS) measures. Also, Adarov and Ghodsi reported that an increase in technical barriers to trade imposed by the host country is associated with higher investment in the foreign subsidiaries operating in this country, pointing to the regulatory barrier-jumping motive of foreign direct investment. Furthermore, Uprasen (2014) examined the impact of non-tariff barriers (NTBs) on exports from China to 14 European Union (EU) countries in the period 1999 to 2010. The empirical findings revealed that the NTBs in the EU market have twofold effects on China's exports. The NTBs have no significant impact on general exports. Nonetheless, the NTBs create both positive and negative effects, depending on the diverse grouping of products exported. Besides, the sanitary and phytosanitary measures tend to hamper overall exports, whereas the technical barriers to trade (TBTs) tend to support overall exports.

Nikomborirak & Fink (2017) examining the Rules of Origin in services. The study found that the restrictiveness of rules of origin determines the degree of preferences entailed in market-opening commitments, shaping the bargaining incentives of FTAs and their eventual economic effects. Khanal (2016) analysed the rules of Origin in GSP schemes and their impacts on Nepal's exports of tea, carpets, pashmina and handicraft production. The study found that the product must satisfy the conditions to be deemed as originating in the country from which preferential access to the importing country is being sought, that is, they are used to determine the "nationality" of goods traded in international commerce. The findings were similar to what Byrne and Rice (2018) found when estimated the impact of rising non-tariff barriers on Irish-UK goods trade. They in addition found that the possible increase in non-tariff barriers is related with the UK's exit from the European customs union. This is supported by Lufuke (2017), Bwana (2018) and Medeiros (2019).

Shebe (2020) assessed the cross-border challenge affecting revenue collection performance in Tanzania, at Namanga customs station. Then author reported that the

administrative challenges that hinder effective collection of revenue include; trading regulations, tax system, status of trade (formalised vs unformalised), corruption, security, delay due to long procedures and queue, smuggling of goods and improper accounting of foreign currency at the border. Gabagambi (2013) assessed the impact of trade barriers on smallholder farmers in Kongwa and Karagwe Districts in Tanzania. Gabagambi found that delay and bribery at road blocks hinder access to international trade among small businesses. Ruiter, Hadley and Li (2017) assessed the participation of women in cross-border trade and found that, women cross- border traders face different constraints and challenges when trading across EAC borders. These include information asymmetry on export procedures and tariffs, bribery, corruption, higher export costs, gender-based harassments and threats of personal safety.

Despite the fact that NTBs influences growth of small businesses in international trade, little is known on how international trade can improve growth of small businesses. Most reviewed literature focused on NTBs as a challenge toward international trade among small businesses (Ruiter et al., 2017). Also, studies have been conducted to analyse the impact of NTBs on trade volume between trading partners (Santeramo & Lamonaca, 2019). Though Sanjo and Ibrahim (2017) tried to link NTBs and SMEs' growth, their focus was on trade openness and exchange rate. But a comprehensive study to analyse the effect of NTBs in terms of international trade regulations, conditions and specific limitations on the growth of small businesses is missing. Hence there is a need to conduct such a study. This study is an attempt to that end.

Conceptual framework

It is widely acknowledged that realistic technical barrier to trade such as phytosanitary, packaging, labelling, quality and standards crate the possibility for the small businesses to meet those conditions and access international markets. This can increase profitability of small businesses, which eventually lead to growth (Adarov & Ghodsi, 2021). Similarly, minimal regulations such as import license, reduced clearing and administrative procedures, delay and certification of goods can increase firms' profitability hence growth (Shebe, 2020). According to Porteous (2012) and Rahman et al. (2020), reduction in specific limitation to trade increases growth of exporting small businesses.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of NTBs and Small Businesses' Growth
Source: Adarov & Ghodsi (2021), Gabagambi (2013), Bryne & Rice (2018), Porteous (2012) and Rahman et al. (2020)

Hypotheses

In order to attain the objectives of the study, the null hypotheses were developed based on review of relevant and related empirical literature on the impact of NTBs on sales growth of small business. Six hypotheses were formulated based on the independent variables of the study. Hypotheses of the study stand out from competitive advantage and new trade theories. Also, the hypotheses were based on the reviewed literature. The following hypotheses have been developed and tested;

- **H₁**: There is no positive and significant association between quality management standards and sales growth of small businesses
- **H₂**: There is no positive and significant relationship between certificate of origin and sales growth of small businesses
- **H₃**: There is no direct and significant link between product classification and sales growth of small businesses
- **H₄**: Sanitary and phytosanitary measures has no positive and significant association with sales growth of small businesses
- **H₅**: Packaging and labelling has no positive and significant link with sales growth of small businesses
- **H₆**: There is no direct and significant link between custom procedures and sales growth of small businesses

Methodology

Study Area, Research Approach and Design

This study took place in Dar es Salaam City in the United Republic of Tanzania (URT). The Dar es Salaam City was selected because it is a commercial centre of the country and thus most exporting small businesses are located (Mpunga, 2016). The study took place Temeke and Ubungo districts due to high presence of small businesses (Sutton & Olomi, 2012). The correlational design was applied because is the best design to systematically examine the association between two variables (Creswell, 2014). Therefore, correlational design was used to estimate the link between NTBs and small businesses' growth. Thus, only quantitative approach was applied in this study.

Target Population, Sampling methods and Sample size

The population for the study comprised all small businesses located in Dar es Salaam City that deal with exportation of goods to different parts of the world. According to Mpunga (2016), there are 637 small businesses in Dar es Salaam City that deals with export trade. However, the sampling frame includes only small businesses located in Temeke and Ubungo district. The stratified random sampling technique was employed to select small businesses in Temeke and Ubungo districts. The reason of using stratified

sampling was the fact that target population comprised of strata based on location (districts). Therefore, before sample was drawn, sample size was determined using Yamane's 1967 formula. The Yamane's formula is expressed as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

Where;

n = Sample size

N = Total number of target population

e = Precision (5%)

Using Yamane formula, the calculation of sample size is as follows:

$$n = 637 / (1 + 637(0.05)^2)$$

$$n_0 = 240$$

Therefore, the sample size was 240 small businesses. Thereafter, small businesses were grouped on the bases of district they are located. Then, the number of small businesses from Temeke (350) and Ubungu (287) was established. Then, proportional sample was estimated for Temeke and Ubungu districts using Cochran (1977) proportionate formula. Based on the calculation 132 and 108 small business were sample from Temeke and Ubungu districts respectively. The Cochran formula is given as follows;

$$n_h = \left(\frac{N_h}{N} \right) \cdot n$$

Where;

n_h = the sample size in stratum h, h_1 = Temeke (132) and h_2 = Ubungu (108)

N_h = the population size in stratum h_1 (350) or h_2 (287),

N = the total population size (637)

n = the total sample size of the study (240).

After that, from every district the required number of small businesses was randomly selected. From every selected small business, the owner/manager were enquired to provide the information regarding the connection between NTBs and growth of their businesses. The stratified method has been chosen since it ensures selection of true representative sample when the population under investigation comprises different sub-groups (Kothari, 2004).

Data collection

The main method of collecting data of this study was survey questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered in form of structured interview. In this study 240 questionnaires were administered and all were usable for data analysis. This is equivalent to a response rate of 100%. Moreover, document analysis was used to collect data concerning sales growth from business transactions records. Moreover, this method was applied to collect data from journal articles, government reports on NTBs.

Data analysis

This study applied descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression model for data analysis. Descriptive statistics will map the degree of NTBs. The multiple linear regression techniques were used to estimate the relationship between NTBs and small business growth. To run regression analysis independent variables measured in five-point Likert scale were entered in the regression model to estimate their impact on dependent variable ‘sales growth’.

Analytical Models

Multiple linear regression models were estimated to analyse anticipated relationship between NTBs and small businesses’ sales growth. The general linear regression model provided in equation (1) was utilised.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + \beta_6X_6 + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where;

- Y = Growth (Sales growth)
- β_0 = Intercept (Constant)
- β_1 = Quality management certification
- β_2 = Certificate of origin
- β_3 = Product classification
- β_4 = Sanitary and Phytosanitary measures
- β_5 = Packaging and labelling
- β_6 = Custom procedures
- X_1 = Quality management certification
- X_2 = Certificate of origin
- X_3 = Product classification
- X_4 = Sanitary and Phytosanitary measures
- X_5 = Packaging and labelling
- X_6 = Custom procedures
- ε = Error term for the model

Variables of linear regression

Table 1. Summary of the Definition of Variables based on NTBs

Variable	Variable Type	Expected Sign	Measurement
Dependent variable			
Sales growth	Continuous	N/A	Numerical
Independent variables			
Technical barrier to trade	Categorical	-	Ordinal: 5 Point Likert Scale:
i. Quality management certification			
ii. Certificate of origin			
iii. Product classification			
iv. Sanitary and Phytosanitary measures			
v. Packaging and Labeling			
vi. Custom procedures			

Findings and Discussion

Demographic Characteristics of Small business Managers/Owners

A researcher surveyed 240 small business managers/owners in Temeke and Ubungo districts. The results in Table 2 show that among them 32.0% were female and 68.0% were male small business owners/managers. The results show that male small business owners/managers who are engaged in international trade are more than female in the study area. This finding corroborates with Mbo'o-Tchouawou et al. (2016), Ruiter, Hadley and Li (2017), Gaka (2018), Siu (2019), UNCTAD (2020) and Parshotam and Balongo (2020). Moreover, Table 2 shows that most surveyed small business owners/managers possessed 40-49 years of age who comprised of 37.0% of the 240 manager/owners. Moreover, those who have 30-39 years and 50-59 years were 27.0% and 20.0%. The lower end comprised those with 20-29 years of age and more than 60 years of age who were 12.0% and 4.0% respectively. This implies that most of small business owners/managers were middle aged and were economically active.

Table 2. Demographic Characteristics of Small Business Owners/Managers (n=240)

Variable/parameter	Measurement	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	163	68.0
	Female	77	32.0
Age	20-29 Years	88	37.0
	30-39 Years	65	27.0
	40-49 Years	48	20.0
	50-59 Years	29	12.0
	60+ Years	10	4.0
Business experience	0-≤1 Year	14	6.0
	>1-4 Years	30	12.0
	>4-7 Years	81	34.0
	>7+	115	48.0
Education level	Primary	14	6.0
	Secondary	29	12.0
	Diploma	101	42.0
	Bachelor	106	44.0
	Masters	3	1.5

Furthermore, results in Table 2 indicate that most small business owners/managers had more than seven years of experience in international trade, who are categorized as highly experienced. This group constituted 48.0%. Moreover, those with 4-7 years experience (good experience) were 34.0%. Therefore, majority of small business owners/managers had considerable experience in international trade. Therefore, this study implies that surveyed small business owners/managers had enough experience to understand the impact of technical barriers to trade. In addition, results in Table 2 show that 44.0% and 42.0% of surveyed small business owners and managers had university degrees and certificate/diploma education respectively. Besides, the results show that 12.0% of surveyed small business owners/managers possess secondary education while 6.0% of

small business owners/managers were found to possess primary education. The results imply that most of small business owners/managers are regarded as knowledgeable enough to understand different issues pertaining to international trade and technical barriers to trade.

Descriptive statistics

Table 3 shows that all six variables of technical barrier to trade have positive skewness values that range between -0.5 to 0.5, which means that the data is symmetrical and have flat tails that are similar to normal distribution data set. In addition, the variables have kurtosis value less than 3 (Kurtosis value >3), which means the data variables are consistent and normally distributed. The results show that the data set was mesokurtic and has tails similar to normally distributed data set. This means that the six variables have lower tail and stretched around the centre. Thus, skewness and kurtosis suggest that technical barrier to trade applied for small business influences their participation in international trade and hence their sales growth.

Furthermore, mean scores of four variables of construct technical barrier to trade, namely, quality management certification, sanitary and phytosanitary measures and packaging and labelling fall under the Likert scale value of strongly agree while variable product classification have mean score in a scale of agree. This signifies that small business managers or owners had largely agreed that technical barrier to trade such as quality management standards, certificate of origin, product classification, sanitary and phytosanitary measures and packaging and labelling to a larger extent influences their sales growth. The findings corroborate with Uprasen (2014), Chukwuma, Ezenyilimba, and Agbara (2018), Tusiime (2019), Adarov and Ghodsi (2021), Flach and Unger (2021) Amadi (2022) and Laget and Deuss (2023) who reported that technical barrier to trade can facilitate international trade thereby increasing business and national income.

On the contrary, variable custom procedures have a mean score that falls into disagree category ($M=1.45$, $SD=637$). There are mixed results regarding effective implementation of custom procedures that help small business in international trade. This finding is in line with Nkuna (2014), Masinde (2015), Masinjila (2018) and Shebe (2020) who reported that despite simplification of documentation; streamlining and harmonization of custom procedures restriction to international exist especially to small business. However, this study acknowledges that under the OSBP strategy length and complicated documentations and custom procedures had been simplified and streamlined respectively to assist small trader's access foreign markets. Also, procedures have been harmonised to eliminate repetition and duplication of documentations and clearance process. The proponents of OSBP argue that, it has reduced delay and increased efficiency in flow of products and services to international markets (Leyaro, 2021), enhanced interconnectedness and reduced logistics and trade costs caused by delay at the border (Zgovu, 2021). Moreover, OSBPs have integrated systems, infrastructure, and inter-agency cooperation for trade facilitation (Adarov & Ghodsi, 2021).

Table 3. Measures of Central Tendency for Technical Barrier to Trade (n=240)

Technical barrier to trade	N	Mean	S. D	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Stat	Stat	Stat	Stat	Std. Error	Stat	Std. Error
Quality management certification	240	4.08	.706	-.108	.211	-.968	.419
Certificate of Origin	240	3.12	1.178	.071	.211	.439	.419
Product Classification	240	3.01	1.192	-.021	.211	.079	.419
Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures	240	4.30	.643	-.555	.211	-1.061	.419
Packaging and Labelling	240	4.17	.688	-.329	.211	-1.567	.419
Custom Procedures	240	1.45	.637	1.050	.211	1.820	.419

Inferential statistics

The findings in Table 4 show that R is 0.994. This is very high correlation indicates a good level of prediction between variables of technical barrier to trade and sales growth of small business. This R value (0.994) signifies that our model predicts technical barrier to trade quite correctly. The R-Square has a value of 0.991, which means that the independent variables based on technical barrier to trade (quality management certification, certificate of origin, product classification, sanitary and phytosanitary measures, packaging and labeling and custom procedures) explain 99.1% of the variability of the dependent variable (sales growth of small business), whilst 0.9% (100%-99.1%) of the variation is caused by factors other factors that are not included in this model. Also, adjusted R² is 0.990 indicating that 99.0% of variation in the sales growth of small business is correctly explained by the technical barrier to trade variables, which are specified in the model. In addition, there is small discrepancy 0.001 (.991-.990) between the values of R-squared and Adjusted R Square, which means the specified model fits well.

Table 4. Technical Barrier to Trade Model Summary (n=240)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.994 ^a	.991	.990	.19009

a. Predictors: Constant, quality management, certificate of origin, product classification, sanitary and phytosanitary, packaging and labeling, custom procedures

Furthermore, Table 4 shows that the standard error of estimates shows that on average, our estimates of sales growth of small business was wrong by .19 which is small and thus cannot be taken into account. In addition, the results in Table 5 show that the independent variables statistically significantly predict the dependent variable, $F(6, 233) = 5648.102$,

p (.000). The F-ratio in the ANOVA, tests whether the overall regression model is a good fit for the data. Thus, the value of F ratio shows that the specified regression model is a good fit of the data. Table 5 shows that standardized coefficients for packaging and labelling was the highest predictor contributing (0.538) to explain sales growth of small business, followed by quality management certification (0.478), custom procedures (0.445), sanitary and phytosanitary measures (0.416), certificate of origin (0.072) and lastly is product classification (0.057). Standardized coefficients measure how much the dependent variable increases when the independent variable is increased by one unit of standard deviation supposing that other variables in the model are held constant. It is useful measure to rank the independent variables based on their absolute contribution in explaining the dependent variable.

Table 5. ANOVA for Technical Barrier to Trade (n=240)

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	612.011	6	205.002	5648.102	.000 ^b
	Residual	4.101	233	.037		
	Total	616.112	239			

a. Dependent Variable: sales growth

b. Predictors: Constant, quality management, certificate of origin, product classification, sanitary and phytosanitary, packaging and labeling, custom procedures

The findings in the Table 6 also allow us to check significance and predictive contribution of predictor variables, but also for multicollinearity. The findings show that Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for all predictor variables was <10 and Tolerance >0.1. The criteria for multicollinearity free model state that the VIF should be <10 (or Tolerance >0.1) for all variables in the regression model (Belsley, 1991; Shrestha, 2020). Therefore, since all predictor variables in this model do not violate the criteria; then there was no multicollinearity in the estimated model. The results in Table 6 show that the constant 0.109 is the predicted value for the dependent variable if all independent variables take a value of 0. It means that an average sales growth of small business would be 0.109 when all predictor variables take the value zero.

Table 6. Regression Results for Technical Barrier to Trade

Mode	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	.109	.095		1.151	.249		
Quality Management Standards	1.153	.020	.478	57.630	.000	.857	1.170
Certificate of Origin	.145	.233	.072	.623	.534	.415	2.411
Product Classification	.135	.183	.057	.735	.464	.642	1.557

Mode	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
Sanitary and Phytosanitary	1.080	.022	.416	49.101	.000	.823	1.214
Packaging and labelling	1.231	.161	.538	7.640	.000	.789	1.268
Custom Procedures	-1.142	.022	.445	-51.899	.000	.801	1.250

a. Dependent Variable: Sales Growth

Furthermore, Table 6 shows that quality management certification has positive and highly significant ($\beta=1.153$; $p=.000$) <0.05) relationship with sales growth of small business. The beta coefficient value means that every unit increase in quality management standards increases 1.105 in sales growth generated by the small businesses. The standard error of estimate ($SE=0.02$) implies that there is a small chance that the estimate could be wrong. Therefore, the hypotheses H_1 : *There is no positive and significant association between quality management standards and sales growth of small businesses* was rejected. The plausible explanation is that, offering best quality products for export help the small business to access international market and hence increase their sales volume. The idea of quality management standards aimed to aid international trade by assuring customer satisfaction and as a result enlarges their sales in international markets. Most times the international buyers face greater transactions costs and information asymmetries, which constrain international trade. Therefore, quality management certifications allow small business to communicate with international buyers about the quality of their products, which can reduce international buyers' uncertainties and transaction cost, and be beneficial to trading relationships. This is corroborated by Fiankor, Martinez-Zarzoso and Brummer (2019) and Flach and Unger (2021). Though, small businesses in developing country face the stigma that they produce products of lower quality than developed countries, quality management certification may provide them with a chance to access the international market and thus boost their sales.

However, predictor *certificate of origin* has positive but not significant ($\beta=.145$; $p=.534$) >0.05) relationship with sales growth of small business. Thus, the hypothesis H_2 : *There is no positive and significant relationship between certificate of origin and sales growth of small businesses* failed to be rejected. This means that the predictor certificate of origin is not useful in the model, when the other variables are already in the model. In other words, independent variable *certificate of origin* do not provide meaningful explanations on dependent variable *sales growth* because there is no substantial evidence to explain the relationship between the two variables. Similarly, the findings show no significant relationship between product classification and small businesses' sales growth ($\beta=.135$; $p=.464$) >0.05). Thus, the study failed to reject hypothesis H_3 : *There is no direct and significant link between product classification and sales growth of small businesses*. Basically, the reasonable clarification is that, there is lack of proper evidence to substantiate effect of product classification on the sales growth of small business. Despite this, literature have shown that in developing countries small business are constrained from participating in international trade and hence their growth due to presence of

numerous technical barriers to trade, which are unnecessarily applied with trading partners especially the developed countries (Brenton & Soprano, 2018; Leyaro, 2021; Mpunga, 2016; Sanjo & Ibrahim, 2017). For instance, though Tanzania has ratified AGOA and other trade facilitation agreements with developed countries but is still difficult to sell to those countries (Nkuna, 2014; Masinde, 2015; TPSF, 2017; EAC, 2018).

Regarding predictor sanitary and phytosanitary measures, it has positive ($\beta=1.060$) and highly significant ($p=.000 < 0.05$) impact on sales growth of small business. The regression coefficient ($\beta=1.080$) means that every unit increase in SPS measures expands sales of small businesses in international trade by 1.060 units. In addition, the standard error of estimate reveals a small chance 0.022 that the regression estimate for this model could be wrong. Therefore, hypothesis H_4 : *Sanitary and phytosanitary measures have no positive and significant association with sales growth of small businesses* was rejected. Thus, the study implication is that application of sanitary and phytosanitary measures expands sales volume of small business in foreign market. Compliance to safety measures improves buyers' confidence toward products and thus their buying frequency increases. The findings are in line with Kang and Ramizo (2017) and Adarov and Ghodsi (2021) who found that SPS facilitate trade and according to Crivelli and Groeschl (2016), eventually increase sales.

According to ADB (2014), Murina and Nicita (2014) and Edewa (2016), small business in developing countries compared to those in developed countries, find it difficult to comply to SPS measures due to associated high trade cost that lower their profit. However, it is widely agreed that these costs can be acceptable due to the importance of human, animal, and plant safety and more importantly expansion of international trade through an access to international market. This is supported by Babatunde (2018), Ali (2016) and Laget and Deuss (2023). The aim of SPS measures is to tell international consumers that are safe and thus can consume imported products with assurance of their health. Thus, they are very crucial in development and sustainability of international trade and in particular they enhance small businesses' access to international market. The Standards and Trade Development Facility (2017) and Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development [OECD], (2021) reported that SPS measures has positive impact on expansion of international trade for small businesses and thus increases their sales.

Moreover, the findings in Table 6 show that packaging and labelling has a positive and highly significant association ($\beta=1.231$, $p=.000 < 0.05$) with sales growth of small business. This implies that every unit change in proper packaging and labelling of export products increases sales growth of small business by 1.231 units. The standard error of estimate ($SE=0.161$) shows that there is greater chance that the coefficient of estimate is correct.

H_5 : *Packaging and labelling have no positive and significant link with sales growth of small businesses* was rejected. The plausible explanation is that proper packaging and labelling are applicable in increasing sales volume of small business in international trade. Also, Wyrwa and Barska (2017) iterated the importance of packaging for increasing sales. In addition, Van Rompay, Deterink and Fenko (2016) and Gordon and Williams (2020)

reported that labeling help buyer to identify and differentiate a product from others and expresses the content of the product to the consumer so that to stimulate buying. Consumers more and more depend on the information available on or in the packaging that indicate quality attributes and compares it with the information on labels of other products to determine the expected quality and on basis of the information make decisions to buy or not to buy a product. In marketing packaging and labeling is also part of promotional and advertising campaigns in order to inform and increase sales. Though packaging and labeling increases operational costs (Mohammadi, Hnzayy & Azad, 2014), they have positive and significant impact on sales growth of small business in international markets (Chukwuma et al., 2018; Ciechomski, 2008; Tusiime, 2019).

Table also 6 show that custom procedures has negative and highly significant impact ($\beta=1.142$, $p=.000$) <0.05) on sales growth of small business. This signifies that an increase in custom procedure by one unit decreases sales growth of small business by 1.142 units. The standard error of estimate ($SE=0.022$) shows that there is small chance that the coefficient of estimate could be incorrect. Therefore, this study rejected the hypothesis H_6 : *There is no direct and significant link between custom procedures and sales growth of small businesses.*

Thus, the findings signify that the custom procedures restrict international trade among small business, and thus their sales growth. This finding is corroborated by Muqayi and Manyeruke (2015), Cheruiyot and Rotich (2018) and Kundabaramye (2021) who found that custom procedures restrict the participation of small-scale international traders in the foreign markets of EAC and SADC members countries.

Though the establishment of OSBPs to address the challenges of lengthy and repetitive custom procedures had reaped some benefits, but Shebe (2020) found that there are custom procedures that hinder small business to access international market at Namanga OSBP due to futile trading regulations, low accountability of OSBP officers, bureaucracy among OSBP officers, corruption and bribery among border officers and outdated technology. Also, Mugayi (2015) and Masinjila (2018) found that small businesses face numerous challenges that restrict access to international trade at Chirundu and Busia OSBP respectively. In essence, participation in international markets provides an opportunity for small business to sell more goods and services but also access to lucrative markets that fetch handsome prices compared to local markets. This is supported by Fitzgerald and Halle (2018), Autor, Dorn, Hanson, Pisano & Shu (2020) and Hayakawa, Ishikawa and Tarui (2020). As such, custom procedures impede the growth of small business.

Conclusion and Implications

Conclusion

The general finding of the study leads to the conclusion that, technical barriers to trade leads to increase in sales growth of small businesses through an increased access to international market. The improvement in quality of products for export provides chance to small business to participate in international market and thereby improve their sales. This is the same to packaging and labelling as well as safety management of export

products through sanitary and phytosanitary measures. Though compliance to these technical barriers to trade has cost implication to small businesses profitability, their benefits outweigh the incurred cost. Moreover, this study concludes that small businesses are restricted from participating in international trade by complex custom procedures, which increases time spend at the border and trade related costs. Though improvement of custom procedures through OSBPs has enabled number of small traders to access foreign market, the problems still exist. In addition, this study concludes that certificate of origin and product classifications do not have any vivid impact on small business sales growth. Based on the existing debate on the influence technical barriers to trade on growth of small business, it's now established that, technical barriers to trade when applied correctly as stipulated by World Trade Organisation have potential to increases participation of small business in international trade, and hence increase their sales growth.

Implications

Theoretical implication

This study has provided a theoretical review of competitive advantage theory and new trade theory to understand the extent of technical barriers to trade impact sales growth of small business. The theories assisted in building and testing theoretical framework underpinning the application of technical barriers to international trade to enhance foreign market access among small business. Although some variables in this study were borrowed from previous literature, most of them were provided by competitive advantage (demand conditions such as quality of products, safety, packaging and labeling) and new trade theories (certificate of origin, product classification, product quality, safety, packaging and labeling). As such, the theoretical and conceptual framework of this study provides a holistic approach to analysing the impact of non-tariff barriers to international trade on growth of small business sales volume.

Practical implication

The findings of the study bring knowledge contribution by adding in empirical literature of technical barriers to trade in relation to international market and sales growth of small businesses.

Study limitations

This study has several unavoidable limitations. The scope of this study was limited to technical barriers to trade as one form non-tariff barriers to international trade. Other barriers include specific limitation and registrations or license requirements. The present study can be broaden further by adding specific limitations on trade such as embargo, import ban and sanctions, subsidies and minimum import price and quota. Also, demographic characteristics of managers/owners and business can be used to broaden the scope of the study as important variables of small business owners/managers as well as of a business entity, which could play the same crucial part in determining the impact of NTBs on the sales growth of small businesses.

Study Recommendations

Based on the findings it is recommended to the government to harmonise and streamline custom procedures so that they become helpful to small business through trade facilitation instead of restricting trade. Moreover, custom documentations should be simplified to allow small traders participate and access international market.

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